

**ZIMBABWE NATIONAL DEFENCE
UNIVERSITY**

**CENTRE FOR DEFENCE AND SECURITY STUDIES
NATIONAL DEFENCE COURSE**

**STRATEGIES TO IMPLEMENT MILITARY OPERATIONS
OTHER THAN WAR IN ZIMBABWE**

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ABSTRACT

The defence forces have constitutional mandate to protect citizens, territorial integrity, national security and interests, and to uphold the constitution through the use of both combat and non-combat means. Combat capability in many developing nations is weak. On the other hand, the military is often abused and positioned at centre of corruption and bad governance under the banner of non-combat operations also known as military operations other than war (MOOTW). The study interrogated strategies to effectively implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe. Effective MOOTW implementation strategies have impact on national security policy, and it also professionalises the conduct of the defence force in the civil-military relations spectrum. A mixed research methodology was adopted in order to obtain both qualitative and quantitative data to analysis MOOTW implementation strategies. The study was guided by civil-military relations concepts mainly Huntington`s subjective and objective models of civilian control of the military. The study mainly focused on three strategies; funding, support and awareness-related strategies. The results indicate that public awareness campaign strategies are considered the most effective way to promote MOOTW implementation: public awareness strategies (98%), civil ministries support strategies (85%) government funding strategies (81%) and non-state funding strategies (21%). It is important to note that strategies that promote public awareness on the importance of MOOTW create a common vision among the military and civil society. The military-society synergies resonate with military constitutional mandate and further broaden the scope of peace and development efforts by all citizens. Effective MOOTW implementation strategies can change the narrative that the military is at the core of bad governance, corruption and continuous struggles for power in developing nations.

Key Words: *military operations other than war (MOOTW), Zimbabwe Defence Forces (ZDF,) civil-military relations, development, security, national security.*

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DECLARATION

I, Godwin VHUMBA, do hereby declare that the work presented in this document entitled: *Strategies to implement military operations other than war in Zimbabwe*, is my own work and all the sources that I quoted have been indicated and acknowledged by means of complete references.

DEDICATION

Dedicated to all Africans who devoted their time and energy to restore the dignity of fellow Africans. I salute you all, God bless my family and Zimbabwe!

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I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Brigadier General, Dr J Chikanga who provided professional assistance and constructive comments and academic direction to this study.

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Finally, the views expressed in this study do not in any way represent the official position of the ZDF. It is purely my paper for military studies, a humble contribution to the implementation of MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AFZ	Air Force of Zimbabwe
AFZ HQ	Air Force of Zimbabwe Headquarters
CMR	Civil-Military Relations
MDC	Movement for Democratic Change
MOD	Ministry of Defence
MOOTW	Military Operations Other Than War
PLA	People's Liberation Army
RSF	Rhodesian Security Forces
UN	United Nations
ZANLA	Zimbabwe African National Liberation Army (),
ZDF	Zimbabwe Defence Forces
ZIPRA	Zimbabwe People's Revolutionary Army
ZNA	Zimbabwe National Army
ZNDU	Zimbabwe National Defence University

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This study proposes to examine military operations other than war implementation strategies in Zimbabwe. This chapter among other issues outlines the background of the study, statement of the problem, the underlying conceptual framework, research objectives, research questions, significance of the study, research methodology, delimitations of the study, and limitations, as well as the ethical considerations. The study was framed under the civil military relations and military operations other than war concepts. The aim of the study is to examine the implementation strategies of the conduct of non-combat roles of the military in Zimbabwe to achieve sustainable national security.

1.2 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Military operations other than war (MOOTW) is an established global military concept adopted by contemporary countries with different objectives. The main objective is to respond to non-traditional threats to national security. The armed forces of many countries, US, China, Russia and India among others are involved in these operations. MOOTW is often contested as military intervention in national and domestic political, social and economic affairs. The conduct of MOOTW in Zimbabwe raised mixed feelings among various sectors of the national and international community.

African militaries have influenced development and governance in many post-colonial countries. They either have a positive or negative influence. Some have, fought liberation wars that ended colonialism and others heavily participated in the promotion of authoritarian rule. The military, therefore, has become a very important institution in Africa. The western concept that the military should be under civilian control was adopted by many countries for

various reasons. The civil-military relations that developed in post-colonial Africa naturally became different from those of the western countries. Ngoma (2006) observes that the socio-political history and the unstable environment created a special context which affected all actors in civil-military relations. Civil-military relations have become vital in the study of post-colonial African governance and development challenges. This has also affected the response of African militaries non-traditional threats to national security.

In many African states, it is generally believed that bad governance has retarded development. With the high demand for democratisation and good governance African military activities have come under heavy scrutiny. For instance, the deployment of ZDF into the Democratic Republic of Congo is often cited as one of the major causes of the drastic downfall of the Zimbabwean economy. ZIDERA S (4) (1) states that:

Through economic mismanagement, undemocratic practices, and the costly deployment of troops to the Democratic Republic of the Congo, the Government of Zimbabwe has rendered itself ineligible to participate in International Bank for Reconstruction and Development and International Monetary Fund programs.

The high demand for good governance, social and economic development in many African communities forces many actors to analyse the role of African militaries' involvement in states' development agenda. African militaries' contribution to 'bad governance' became a concern to the international donor community as evidenced by the World Bank's (WB) Structural Adjustment Programmes (SAPs) which called for reductions in defence budget was presumed as a concern by the International donor community to the bad governance as a result of the involvement of African militaries in state development. Again these calls failed to solve African development challenges related to the military. For the Zimbabwean case, the US Congress through ZIDERA in 2001 S (4)(d)(5), went further to prescribe that "The

Zimbabwean Armed Forces, the National Police of Zimbabwe, and other state security forces are responsible to and serve the elected civilian government”. It is important to note that under the Chinese Socialist Democracy, loyalty to the party is of paramount importance. Addressing the PLA troops , China’s President and military leader, Xi Jinping, in December 2012 clearly articulated that “top priority” was for the military to win battles, and “the soul of the military” was obeying the Party’s command (Xinhua News Agency, 2012).

These differences in how the government should engage the military in non-combat roles (MOOTW) is a real challenge in many developing countries. Many countries are guided by Western democracy in their policy formulation but in practice they do it the Chinese way. Policy and practice are in divergence. Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2010) argues that, *Maoism* had a strange conception of political power as coming from the barrel of the gun. The military and the party are one thing. The contradiction between this Maoist thinking and western concept of civil-military relations makes the conduct of MOOTW very difficult and questionable in many African developing countries.

It is wrong to associate all the human security issues and bad governance in post-independence African states with military’s involvement in governance. In most cases, especially in Southern Africa where the number of coups is very low, this military’s involvement has been in the form of MOOTW. Therefore, these MOOTW are in respond to non-traditional threats to national security since they affect the governments’ ability or perceived ability to deal with development issues such as human security and political stability. The challenge for many African states, therefore, is to determine ways and strategies to effectively employ the military in these roles.

The secondment of military personnel to parastatals and ministries is regarded as militarization of state enterprises, the military involvement in voter education was viewed as

partisan, the involvement in housing construction of schools, houses and roads in support of civil ministries was also received with mixed feelings and the involvement of the military in Marange diamonds resulted in Zimbabwe diamonds being labeled bloody diamonds. All these mixed feelings and different perceptions on military operations affected national security, democracy and development.

The conduct of MOOTW in Zimbabwe raised mixed feelings. National security and development became core issues on party politics. The ZDF's involvement in MOOTW became a national and international subject. Reactions of people to MOOTW always vary. For instance, in the US, Foster (1993:27) points out that, "The primary purpose of the military must change demonstrably and fundamentally-from war fighting to nation building, peacekeeping and humanitarian assistance". On the other hand, Huntington (1957), cited by Ayers (1996:4) argues that, "The military should not be organised or prepared or trained to perform such (noncombat) roles". Nonetheless, the US military doctrine embraces the idea of conducting MOOTW. The Joint Pub 3-07 (1995:1) states, "while we have historically focused on war fighting, our military profession is increasingly changing its focus to a complex array of military operations-other than war".

The Zimbabwe Defence Forces (ZDF) is formed by Zimbabwe National Army (ZNA) and the Air Force of Zimbabwe (AFZ). These two services were formed from the amalgamation of the Zimbabwe African National Liberation Army (ZANLA), Zimbabwe People's Revolutionary Army (ZIPRA) and Rhodesian Security Forces (RSF) in 1980 at the independence of Zimbabwe. The uniqueness of the Zimbabwean military is that ZANLA and ZIPRA were the fighting wings of the major two nationalists' parties, Zimbabwe African National Union (ZANU) and Zimbabwe African People's Union (ZAPU) respectively that

fought for independence. ZANU and ZAPU later joined in 1987 to form ZANU-Patriotic Front (PF). This historical link of the ZDF to ZANU-PF is a very important factor in the study of ZDF civil-military relations and all ZDF non-combat operations.

Negative perceptions and large scale accusations of the military affects national image and are threats to national security. Effective utilisation of the military force in MOOTW gives the nation the opportunity to protect its territorial integrity, sovereignty, national interests and national image without engaging in costly and bloody wars. On the other hand, when a nation fails to identify effective strategies to efficiently use its military to counter non-traditional threats to deter wars and promote peace it would end up in human and material losses. It could also result in losses to previously gained national heritages, national cultures and national image thereby negatively affecting national security. Inadequacies in strategies to utilise the military to counter non-traditional threats will also result in unnecessary foreign interventions that impinge on national security. Countries such as US, China, Russia and India among others have adopted the concept of MOOTW to fight non-traditional threats to national security. Several scholars expressed their views on the ZDF's involvement in national non-combat operations in the social, political, economic, environmental and developmental spheres (Alexander, 2013; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2006; Moyo, 2015; Williamson, 2010). However, some believe the military is inappropriately being used by the state and therefore there is need for civil-military relations reviews and security sector reforms (Chitiyo, 2009; Rupiya 2005; and Nyakudya, 2019). Against a background of direct relationship between military operations other than war and national security, the research aims to examine the strategies for MOOTW implementation in Zimbabwe.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The involvement of the ZDF in social, political and economic national affairs raised mixed feelings among various sectors of the national and international community. State militarisation, regime protection, human rights abuse, corruption and being a partisan force are some of the concerns raised against the ZDF. Negative perceptions large-scale accusations of the military in its non-combat operations affect national image, democracy, peace, development, civil-military relations and national security. This has necessitated the examination of the strategies being used to implement MOOTW by the ZDF.

1.4 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study was guided mainly by civil-military relations and MOOTW concepts. Ebo (2008) has refers to civil-military relations as the web of relations that connects the military and its society. Similarly, Rupiya (2003:252) refers to civil-military relations as “a complex set of interrelationships, established norms and practices between the triad – the state, society and the armed forces”. Ngoma (2004) argues that civil-military relations are a critical subject in the development discourse in Africa, where military involvement in development is always a challenge. Civil-military relations involve a number of issues pertaining to the state, the military and society.

Prominent scholars such as Samuel P. Huntington`s work reveals the place of the military profession in the US society. Goodpaster and Huntington (1977) cited by Rupiya (2003) argue that the American peoples only came to have interests in military affaires after the end of Second World War. The society used to ignore the importance of military professionalism, power and culture. This could have been due to the fact that the analyses of military operations are commonly characterised by secrecy and the issues are then clouded by myths and realities. The military normally deals with issues of national security. Ngoma (2006)

examines African civil-military relations trends focusing on the nexus between military, democracy and politics. He concludes that there was a general acceptance that western countries have relative longer history of mature politics and democratic civil-military relations than the African countries. This has to some extent hindered the developments to open discuss the non-combat roles of the military, even though they are very important in the African context.

Conceptual Framework: Possible Strategies to Implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe

1.5 OBJECTIVES

- a. To determine the effectiveness of funding MOOTW as a strategy to implement the operations in Zimbabwe.
- b. To establish effectiveness of supporting civil ministries in their affairs/projects as a strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.
- c. To determine the effectiveness of awareness /educational curriculum changes as a strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

1.6 QUESTIONS

- a. Can funding MOOTW be an effective strategy to implement these operations in Zimbabwe?
- b. Can supporting civil ministries in their affairs/projects be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
- c. Can awareness programmes be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is premised on the belief that a situational analysis of the ZDF MOOTW can help not only the military to have self-evaluation of its operations, but for all Zimbabweans to have a common vision, working towards peace and development together with their defence forces.

African militaries are often abused by politicians, it is also equally important to point out that the military often abuse their citizens to advance of personal interests under the cover of national interest. The phenomenon of non-traditional security threats is on the rise worldwide, challenging national cohesion and social order. Developing countries are confronted with numerous non-traditional threats to national security. The involvement of the military in MOOTW is one of the grand strategies often employed to counter the non-traditional threats to national security. As highlighted earlier, MOOTW focuses on deterring war, resolving conflict, promoting peace and supporting civil authorities in response to domestic crisis. The study has potential to assist policy makers on the implementation of MOOTW to enhance national security. The Study will also equip military officers with necessary skills to effectively counter non-traditional threats to national security. Therefore the research will

explore and examine strategies to operationalize MOOTW, so that appropriate policies and programmes may be formulated and effectively implemented.

The study will add to the existing body of knowledge on MOOTW in Zimbabwe and its implications to national security.

1.8 DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study focused on the MOOTW by ZDF. The focus was on non-combat activities of the military guided by MOOTW principles.

1.9 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Research participants may not answer all questions. Authorisation letter was used to support the explanations to the research participants that data gathered will be used for academic purposes only.

1.10 DEFINITION OF KEY TERMS

The Chinese People's Liberation Army (PLA) published that MOOTW indicates the military operations to realise certain political, economic, social or military purposes with armed forces that do not have the nature of war (Zhang, 2014).

MOOTW are those operations undertaken by military forces to safeguard their country's national security and developmental interests, that do not constitute a war (Gaoyue and James, 2019:3).

Ebo (2008) has refers to civil-military relations as the web of relations that connects the military and its society.

National Security. James defines national security as an appropriate and aggressive blend of nation's resilience and military power for the protection of a nation's human and other

resources, territorial integrity interests, core values and pursuance of a nation's benefits and well-being of the citizens (James, 2012:75).

1.11 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The chapter presented introduction to the whole study by covering background to the study, statement of the problem, the underlying conceptual framework, research objectives, research questions, significance of the study, research methodology, delimitations of the study, and limitations, as well as the ethical considerations. The study aims to examine the implementation strategies of MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The next chapter examines literature related to the study.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter provided the introduction to the whole research study by presenting an overview of the ground to be covered on strategies to operationalise MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The core of this chapter is to interrogate the views of various scholars regarding the strategies adopted to implement MOOTW. The review focuses on the concept of MOOTW, the overarching theories on civil-military relations and empirical review on MOOTW implementation strategies. The strategies include, unity integrity strategies, regional alliances strategies, public affairs/ media coverage strategies, civil affairs strategies, psychological operations (psyop) strategies, coordination with NGOs and PVOs strategies and education and training strategies among others.

2.2 MOOTW AND RELATED CONCEPTS

The section addresses the key aspects of MOOTW including the definitions, principles, the development of MOOTW, types and characteristics of MOOTW and finally assessed MOOTW contributions to national security.

2.2.1 Definitions

One major challenge in studying MOOTW is defining the term itself as there are as many definitions as there are authors. The acronym MOOTW was introduced in the United States military during the 1990s. The Joint Doctrine for Military Operations Other Than War of the US regards the concept as focusing on deterring war, resolving conflict, promoting peace, and supporting civil authorities in response to domestic crisis (US Joint Publication 3-07, 1995).

The Chinese People's Liberation Army (PLA) regards MOOTW as military operations to realise certain political, economic, social or military purposes with armed forces that do not have the nature of war (Zhang, 2014).

The above definitions seem to agree that MOOTW can be viewed differently from war operations. However, one may safely conclude that the Chinese perspective has broader scope, as the military can openly be engaged to achieve a wide range of developmental goals. In this regard MOOTW can be referred as those operations undertaken by military forces to safeguard their country's national security and developmental interests, that do not constitute a war (Gaoyue and James, 2019:3). This most recent definition from Gaoyue and James was considered more appropriate for this study as it emphasises that MOOTW are undertaken by military forces to safeguard their country's national security.

2.2.2 Principles of MOOTW

The US Joint Publication 3-07, (1995) for MOOTW, identifies six (6) fundamental principles believed to apply in all MOOTW tasks; objective, unity of effort, security, restraint, perseverance, and legitimacy. The first three (3) were derived from the principles of war. The big question is the applicability of these principles in different nations other than the US. In China Gaoyue and James (2019) reports six MOOTW Principles are as follows: acting according to laws and regulations, rapid response and deployment, joint command to unify efforts, effective organisation and civil-military coordination, managing publicity and boosting morale and adhering to United Nations principles.

2.2.3 Characteristics of MOOTW

Patterns of MOOTW are dynamic; they change along with the expansion of national interests and requirements of national security. According to the US Joint Publication 3-07, (1995) MOOTW have the following basic characteristics:

1. Political in Nature

The conduct of MOOTW operations are the same as war operations. They both reflect the strategic interests and political will of the state and all are important means to realise national political objective. But in comparison with war operations, the restriction of politics to the operation process of MOOTW is stricter. The time, method, means, intensity and scale of operations are all strictly restricted under political requirements (US Joint Publication 3-07, 1995).

For example, the US Joint Publication 3-07, (1995) states that there are strict rules for the scale of armed forces to be used in pacifying riots, the situation under which arms can be used, the degree of use of arms and the levels with authority to approve the use of arms. Upon these issues, incautiousness may lead to disastrous political consequences. Besides, international rescue, peace keeping and anti-terrorist operations involve relations with other countries, they are no longer purely military operations, and there are very high political requirements for such operations.

2. Emergency Responds Operations

According to the US Joint Publication 3-07, (1995) MOOTW are divided into two kinds of situations: the first is the security threat that has a process of fermentation, outbreak and escalation. For such kind of threats, there are usually counter plans and operations are carried out according to plans. The second is major emergent event that happens abruptly and is hard to anticipate, this kind of threats are difficult to cope with and are the key issues for the military in their preparations for the MOOTW.

Such kind of events usually has the following characteristics:

- a. *Abrupt and emergent.* For example, terrorist attack or natural disasters like earthquake, flood, fire and tsunami, they usually appear abruptly with unexpected time, location and degree.
- b. *Quick in development, spreading and escalation.* For example, large scale social riots or insurgencies or infectious epidemics.
- c. *Limited favourable time for controlling escalation.* Terrorist events, abrupt natural disasters, massive social riots need to be disposed resolutely, otherwise, favourable chances for control of situation will quickly run away, situation will escalate and bring about disastrous consequences for the national security and lives and properties of the people.

3. Increasingly Normalised Operations

In the present era, wars are more and more restricted by various factors, while non-traditional security threats are on the rise, hence, MOOTW are sharply increased and becoming normalised (US Joint Publication 3-07, 1995). Situations in which we have to cope with such security threats are on the increase. As the military is a highly organized armed group, it is an important force of the state in safeguarding national security and dealing with various major events in peace time.

Gaoyue and James (2019) posit that in concrete operations, this kind of normalized characteristics will be further strengthened through the following two aspects, first, MOOTW are carried out in the whole process of conflict management, thus the duration of military operations will be long, for example, the anti-terrorist, peace keeping, escorting and drug enforcement operations. Second, MOOTW involve more areas, but are less mandatory, sustained operations are needed before they are effective.

4. Flexible Employment of Forces and Means

The employment of forces and means of MOOTW is diversified, sometimes fairly violent means are needed, for example counter terrorism and insurgency pacification; sometimes, means employed are with low intensity, for example, peace keeping, establishment of isolation zones and evacuation of overseas nationals; some other times, there is no need to use violent means, for example, emergency rescue and disaster relief and humanitarian aid operations. These characteristics determine that the employment of forces and means of MOOTW is different from that of war, much more flexible than that.

The flexibility is reflected in the following aspects (US Joint Publication 3-07, 1995):

- a. As MOOTW are carried out in different forms to cope with diversified threats, corresponding forces and means are required to be used flexibly according to the different features and demands of the missions.
- b. In MOOTW, military forces serve as the complement of other national instruments; the subordinate position determines that there must be flexibility in the intensity, scale and time of employment of military forces.
- c. Frequent interagency coordination and operations are needed in MOOTW, the positions of different forces determine that the commanding relations should be established with flexibility. For example, in missions of counter terrorism, insurgency pacification and forceful establishment of isolation zones, operations are usually commanded by the military, other social instruments cooperate; in missions of emergency rescue and disaster relief, operations are usually commanded by government departments, the military cooperate; while in international MOOTW, joint command with foreign militaries are needed.

5. High Operation Transparency

With the development of internet, television and cell phone communication, the social transparency is higher, and as such military operations and even wars can often be broadcasted. Gaoyue and James (2019) also add that MOOTW are mainly used to cope with non-traditional security threats which is highly transparent, therefore, most of MOOTW are carried out under supervision of public media and public voices, whether the MOOTW are carried out in a reasonable and legal way is of great significance to the achievement of the political objective.

2.3 BRIEF HISTORY OF MILITARY OPERATIONS OTHER THAN WAR

This section covers the trends in MOOTW. The study of MOOTW is guided by historical and contemporary literature on studies in other countries and some local cases.

2.3.1 The Evolution of the Doctrine of MOOTW

In the US military history, the concept “Military Operation Other Than War” was put forward in the Doctrine for the Armed Forces of the United States in November 1991. In 1993, the US Doctrine for Joint Operations listed war and operations other than war as the two basic military categories for the first time. In the subsequent year, the Joint Staff Course recognised the importance of MOOTW, “while we have historically focused on war fighting, our military profession is increasingly changing its focus to a complex array of military operations other than war” (Joint Publication 3-07, 1995:1). In China the concept of “military operations other than war” was first introduced in the PLA Training Doctrine version of 2001 (Bifeng, 2013).

2.3.2 Trends on the Nature of Threats to National Security

The changes on the international scale of the nature of threats to national peace and development have transformed the operations of military forces to focus beyond war. This necessitated the introduction of MOOTW which encompasses the use of a wide range of military capabilities. MOOTW centre on deterring war, promoting peace, resolving conflict, and supporting civil authorities in response to domestic crises. For most types of MOOTW, military personnel simply adapt their war fighting skills to the situation. However, for some MOOTW, like humanitarian assistance, war fighting skills are not always appropriate then the focus of MOOTW education would be to ensure that leaders at all levels understand the objectives, principles, and characteristics of MOOTW and can plan and conduct these operations (Bifeng, 2013).

Some believe the rising tide of MOOTW marks a change in military focus, by moving away from war fighting skills towards more non-combat skills. Foster (1993) cited by Ayers (1996) observes that the primary purpose of the military must change demonstrably and fundamentally from war fighting to nation-building, peacekeeping and human assistance. Therefore, the purposes for conducting MOOTW may be multiple, with the importance of such purposes changing according to prevailing conditions. These include; 1) to protect national interests, 2) to deter potential aggressors, 3) to provide humanitarian assistance or 4) to support the United Nations missions (Ayers, 1996).

2.4 THEORIES AND CONCEPTS GUIDING THE STUDY TO IMPLEMENT MOOTW IN ZIMBABWE

This study is anchored on civil-military relations theories and concepts. The section sets out the conceptual framework of the study by examining existing relevant literature on civil-military relations as well as its relevance to MOOTW and national security in Zimbabwe. Civil-military relations form the foundations of strategies applicable to the implementation of MOOTW in any nation.

2.4.1 Civil-Military Relations Theories

The objective and subjective military control models under Huntington's theory of civil-military relations have been internationalized and become the standard way of military control in professional and academic discourse. However, their application in some cases always presents some challenges. In this regard, Nix (2012) observes that when Huntington suggests the theory of civil-military relations he outlined the historical development of military professionalism in Europe and the US with some emphasis on the constitutional requirements and intentions of America's Founding fathers. Nix further observes that Huntington's theory is caught between the variables of military professionalism and the military's participation in the political process.

Subjective Civil Control

Under the Subjective civil control, Huntington (1957:351) emphasises maximising civil power by both civilising and politicising the military. Under this model, civil supremacy is achieved through the integration of the military, political and social systems.

Objective Civil Control

In the objective civil-control model, Huntington (1957) emphasises maximum military professionalism and political neutrality of the military personnel and institutions. He argues that military leadership is driven by professionalism and the most important aspect is giving service to the nation. He concludes that the more professional an army is, the more it takes on the task of serving society. This objective model is well suited for the western parliamentary democracies and for the control of mercenaries or purely conventional militaries. It's not suitable for Africa and particularly Zimbabwe. African militaries should be managed and controlled for both conventional and non-conventional wars. As long as Africa and Zimbabwe have multiparty democracies with overnight political parties the temptation for politicians to meddle in military affairs is high. The nature of African politics does not allow politicians to respect the professional autonomy of the military. They will always manipulate it to further personal or partisan interests.

From a similar perspective Feaver (1999:228) submits that the heart of traditional civil-military relations is a social contract between civilians and the military, maintained in a proper division of labour. The two parties need to clearly define their roles. Any failure to separate the two institutions creates problems such as militarisation of institutions, an issue which was raised by many scholars that include Moyo (2015), Alexander (2013) and Chitiyo (2009) regarding ZDF operations.

Williams (1988) posits that the term civil-military relation is used in the descriptive sense of the word to illustrate the nature of relations between the military and the civilian authorities. It is clear from his observation that each particular society has certain core values that determines the nature of its civil-military relations. The nature of civil-military will determine the scope and application of MOOTW. The civil society and the military should have common understanding on the operations of the military under MOOTW. Such common

understanding will dispel the notions of regime protection, militarisation of state institutions among other accusations associated with MOOTW.

Owens (2013:3) posits that US civil-military relations constitute a bargain, and there are three parties to the bargain: the American people; the government; and the military establishment. Similarly, Rupiya (2003:252) echoed that civil-military relations are defined as representing a complex set of interrelationships, established norms and practices between the triad – the state, society and the armed forces. Therefore it is clear that there is a bargain that binds the three parties which has to be periodically re-negotiated to take account of political, social, technological, or geopolitical changes. The nature of civil-military relations in colonial and post-colonial conditions and in multi-party state conditions is also bound to change. Such a trend analysis might be useful in the study of civil-military relations in Zimbabwe. The trend analysis will make the citizens appreciate the importance of MOOTW. It is only through educational awareness campaigns by the military itself that will make MOOTW acceptable by the citizens. The nation must accept the nature of civil -military relations, and the associated model of civil-military control, as propounded by Huntington. Under the Subjective civil control, Huntington (1957:351) emphasises maximising civil power by both civilising and politicising the military. This is often confused or manipulated by enemies of the state as regime protection. This has negatively affected the conduct of MOOTW.

2.5 LITERATURE REVIEW RELATING TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MOOTW STRATEGIES

The section covers literature on strategies used to implement MOOTW in China and the US militaries. The two countries have different modes of civil military relations but they both use MOOTW to promote national security. The two extreme examples can provide a fair guide in the analysis of the conduct of MOOTW in this study.

2.5.1 China`s Strategies to Implement MOOTW

There are number of strategies used by the Chinese military to implement MOOTW. The following MOOTW implementation strategies were derived from various sources.

Gaoyue and James (2019) posit that the PLA has conducted MOOTW since its inception. However, it was in 2006 that it adopted the term MOOTW. Since the introduction of MOOTW, PLA academic institutions such as Academy of Military Science (AMS) National Defence University (NDU), Army Command College (ACC) and Air Force Command College (AFCC) among others introduced the concept in the their study packages. To date the PLA has produced its own MOOTW reading material. The PLA produced legal documents, manuals, textbooks and researchers contributed large volumes of literature on MOOTW. Several books and articles were produced by researchers at NDU, ACC and AFCC, but the greater part was in Chinese. The PLA produced legal documents and manuals to guide the conduct of MOOTW and these include *Doctrine for Preventing Riots, Regulations for Joint Peacekeeping Operations, Regulations for Participations in Disaster Rescue and Relief and Financial Support for MOOTW* among others. Gaoyue and James (2019) report that teaching and research offices were established in the PLA academic institutions to conduct research and education on non-traditional security (NTS) threats, develop MOOTW theories and to provide consultation for China`s key civil and military decision making.

China is a country with frequent natural disasters. It is one of the most disaster-prone countries in the world. There are various types of disasters in different regions of China with high frequency. Bifeng (2013) describes the 1987 forest fires, the 1998 floods and the 2008 Wen Chuan earthquake to illustrate the extent of natural disasters in China. In May 1987, a catastrophic forest fire in the Greater Khingan Mountains, destroyed 700,000 hectares of

forests, 56,092 people were left homeless, 211 people lost their lives, and the direct economic loss was 500 million RMB. The 1998 heavy floods affected 223 million people and 3004 were recorded dead and the direct economic loss was 166.6 billion RMB.

When an earthquake hit Wen Chuan in 2008, the Chinese military was quickly deployed and rescued over 1.4 million people. In this operation, the Air Force employed more than 100 aircraft and helicopters; they flew totally 850 sorties, 14,700 people and over 3,020 tons of supplies were delivered. It is the largest scale air lift operation in PLA's history of disaster relief (Bifeng 2013). Wei (2012) observed that the army and civilians in China breathe the same air, share their common fate and join their hearts as one.

The Constitution of the People's Republic of China (PRC) states that, "The armed forces of the PRC belong to the people. Its missions are: consolidating national defense, resisting invasion, protecting motherland, defending people's peaceful work, participating in the construction of the country and serving the people with all efforts." In line with this constitutional requirement the concept of MOOTW was then first introduced in the 2001 version of the Training Doctrine of the PLA. The New Ordinance of Military Training published in September 2002 listed the contents of MOOTW as floods fighting, emergency rescue, disaster relief and other emergencies.

The UN Committee of Science and Technology on Disaster Reduction issued a report, in which China was recorded as one of the few countries which suffer from the most severe natural disasters in both mountain areas and coastal regions every year since the time when there is earliest record of human beings. With regards to the 2008 Wen Chuan Earthquake in China, Wei, Dingxin, Zhiyu, Cunhua, Zhenduo, and Chao (2012) concluded that among all

observers , Austria`s Die Presse newspaper gave the highest marks to the Chinese Army , by commenting that there was no nation in the world that can do so well as China when facing disasters.

Former President Hu Jintao: Military Operations Other Than War is becoming an important employment method of military force, we should therefore put the building of MOOTW capability into the overall situation of military modernization and military preparation, to plan and implement it in the scientific way (Bifeng, 2013)

It is important to note that in China, as the former President Hu Jintao explains, MOOTW are becoming an important method of employing the military. They are striving to make scientific ways to prepare and modernise their military through MOOTW. Why not for the Zimbabwean leadership to adopt similar thinking as they use MOOTW to employ the ZDF in the political, social and economic dimensions of national development?

According to Wei *et al* (2012) all things in the Chinese army are based on the principle of “To serve the people”. He further argues that since the PLA was nurtured and supported by the people, the soldiers are supposed to make contribution to people’s living standards. It is believed that only with the national economic growth and improvements of people’s living standards can China spare more resources on national defence construction. This philosophy guides the PLA to contribute a lot to national economy construction. The PLA has, therefore, a long history of providing human, material, and financial support for transportation and infrastructure construction. Wei *et al* (2012) observed that in China it is conventional for the army to do the most difficult job, such as the Qinghai-Tibet and Sichuan-Tibet Highway Construction to link Tibet and mainland.

The PLA soldiers also take part in many key national construction projects that includes transportation and engineering constructions. In order for the PLA to contribute to needs of China's national development, the PLA has established special arms such infrastructure corps and railway corps. The infrastructure corps has completed thousands of national large and medium-sized construction projects and key projects like highways, factories, mines and reservoirs, set up large quantities of buildings for education, scientific research and accommodation for people in Beijing and other big and medium-sized cities. Besides the special arms, other arms like infantry, artillery, armoured force, communication unit special troops, and reconnaissance troops and so on, all make their contribution to economic development without pay.

The PLA soldiers are always playing an important role in China's social and economic development:

- a. Construction in the field of industry, transportation, hydroelectric and telecommunication
- b. Expansion of railways and highways
- c. Reconstruction of airports, harbours and docks
- d. Supported agriculture constructions and improve production conditions
- e. Assist in poverty relief and developments efforts
- f. Public construction in urban and rural areas.

Bifeng (2013) states that new recruits in the PLA receive teachings that the only principle of PLA is; "To serve people wholeheartedly". The idea and value penetrate into every field of the Chinese Army and guide the behaviour of Chinese military men.

The above historical development of MOOTW in the PLA has resulted in several operations that were classified according to Bifeng (2013) into four (4) types, namely:

1) **Operations for Safeguarding Rights and Interest.** These are protective operations to defend sovereignty. The primary missions are:

- a. To patrol the border, territorial air and territorial sea,
- b. To protect fishery and energy exploration,
- c. To prevent and defend enemy's infiltration and sabotage activities that harms China's sovereignty,
- d. To defend the network and electromagnetic space and
- e. To deal with military emergencies in the border region.

2). **Operations for Counter-terrorism and Stability Maintaining.** These are operations to fight against terrorism and to maintain the normal social order. The primary missions are:

- a. To stop terrorists' atrocities, rescue hostage and process the scene of terrorism event;
- b. To annihilate terrorists, destroy their bases;
- c. To secure and guard the vital targets continuously during major occasions;
- d. To deal with group events, put down riots, disturbance and violence and to enforce law and order.

3). **Operations for Emergency Rescue and Disaster Relief**

These are operations to deal with natural disasters, major disasters and serious accidents. The primary missions are:

- a. To deal with flood disaster, wind disaster, snow disaster, tsunami, earthquake, volcanic eruption and aviation disaster;
- b. To prevent infectious diseases from spreading, deal with nuclear, chemical and biological (NCB) accident, maritime distress and aviation disaster and
- c. To rescue and help disaster affected people, transport personnel and materials, repair infrastructure, maintain order in disaster area, eliminate disaster consequences, and assist the post disaster reconstruction.

4). **Operations for Protecting Overseas Interests**

These are operations to support the expansion of national interests, mainly conducted in relevant areas and spaces outside the border. Primary missions are:

- a. To conduct joint training and joint exercise with foreign military;
- b. To employ forces and assets to carry out tasks of rescue, medical treatment and transportation when major crisis occurred;
- c. To escort China`s ocean-going ships, safeguard strategic maritime passages, protect foreign trade and energy import; and
- d. To evacuate the Chinese nationals, overseas residents and materials from disaster areas.

It is important to note that the types of MOOTW vary according to the classification system. Gaoyue and James (2019:4) observe that there are three view points in the classification of MOOTW in the PLA namely:

- a. The 12-type classification system mostly held by professors at NDU which categorises MOOTW into 12 types; deterrence, counter-terrorism, riot suppression, mass event management, border blockage, disaster rescue and relief, nuclear, biological and chemical rescue and relief, air and sea security , air and sea and control, protection of maritime strategic communication lines, international peacekeeping, and overseas rescue and relief.
- b. The 6-type classification system more popular among researchers and active duty personnel at various PLA headquarters which categorises MOOTW into 6 types; counter -terrorism and stability maintenance, operations to safe guard sovereignty and national interests, safety and security, humanitarian assistance and disaster relief, international peace keeping, and international rescue and relief.
- c. The 7-type classification system more popular in the Academy of Military Sciences; counter-terrorism, stability maintenance, disaster rescue and relief, operations to safeguard sovereignty and national interests, safety and rescue operations, international peacekeeping, and overseas rescue and relief.

2.5.2 The United States Strategies to Implement MOOTW

There are number of strategies used by US to implement MOOTW. The strategies are employed according to prevailing situations and intended national security objectives to be achieved. The following MOOTW implementation strategies were derived from the US Joint Pub 3-07 (1995):

1. **Unity Integrity Strategies** - Planners should maintain unity integrity. Military forces train as units and are best able to accomplish a mission when deployed intact. When deployed as integrated units they are able to operate under established procedures and ease to adapt to new situations as required. Unity integrity deployment promotes effectiveness in MOOTW implementation.
2. **Regional Alliances Strategies** - As in combat operations, regional alliances may work to promote MOOTW. In Southern Africa, defence forces often carry joint relief emergency and relief operations. The AFZ often conducts such operations in neighbouring countries. Flood victims in Mozambique are often rescued by the AFZ.
3. **Public Affairs/ Media Coverage Strategies** – Media reporting influences public opinion which affects the success or failure of MOOTW. Public affairs plans should promote open and independent reporting.
4. **Civil Affairs Strategies – Civil Affairs (CA)** units contains personnel with various special skills that support MOOTW. CA units provides assessments of the civil infrastructure, cultures, legal issues, assist in operations of equipment, and serve as liaison between the military and NGOs and PVOs.
5. **Psychological Operations (PSYOP) Strategies** - These strategies can provide significant support in MOOTW. Military PSYOP promote particular themes that can influence attitudes and behaviour.
6. **Coordination with NGOs and PVOs Strategies** - Joint operations with NGOs and PVOs can help promote MOOTW. Structure and size of the joint ops depend on the situation.
7. **Education and Training Strategies** – Adopt MOOTW education to ensure leaders at all levels understand the objectives, principles and characteristics of MOOTW and

can plan and conduct the operations. With some MOOTW types war fighting skills are not always suitable.

2.5.3 Employment of Air Force in the Operations of Emergency Rescue and Disaster Relief

The employment of the Air Force in MOOTW operations is a key factor in both the Chinese and the US military. This is not a stand-alone strategy but a key consideration in the strategies. The use of the air assets complements the efforts of civilian ministries in Emergency Rescue and Disaster Relief operations. The Air Force carries major tasks in the operations of emergency rescue and disaster relief that includes the following:

1. To eliminate, contain or control the sources of disasters.

To eliminate, contain or control the sources of disasters, including spray of fire extinguishing agents, ice breaking in large rivers, and protection of major targets such as large reservoirs, important bridges, li To eliminate, contain or control the sources of disasters, including spray of fire extinguishing agents, ice breaking in large rivers, and protection of major targets such as large reservoirs, important bridges, lines of communication, large projects and military bases.

2. To rescue, transfer and evacuate trapped persons.

To find, rescue and evacuate trapped people in disaster-hit area within the shortest possible time; to set up air medical aid station with medical equipment and personnel on board, or to transfer the injured and the sick to safe area for timely treatment and proper settlement; and to eliminate potential dangers.

3. To rescue critical materials, and to deliver the rescue personnel, relief supplies and equipment.

Relying on the delivery platform like military transporter and transport helicopter, AF is responsible to deliver rescue personnel, relief supplies and equipment, and to recover, evacuate important materials and equipment through air-landing or parachuting within the shortest possible time.

4. To provide support operations.

To learn the disaster situation comprehensively, to control and coordinate rescue forces; to conduct reconnaissance, early warning, air command and control, air communication; to guide the ground troops; to monitor major secondary disasters and major targets; to stabilize the area through air radio broadcasting; and to conduct accompanying support.

5. To participate in recovery and reconstruction of disaster area.

If necessary, the Air Force can provide air support to the local government on recovery and reconstruction. For example, it can help to deal with public health incidents by spreading pesticides, assist engineers on air hoisting work, and provide support in disaster control by monitoring flood flow and protection of water environment.

2.6 KEY CONSIDERATIONS UNDER THE STRATEGIES TO IMPLEMENT MOOTW

There are several factors to be considered in the strategies to implement MOOTW. This study has focused on the following factors as key consideration because of their relevance to the study. There are issues behind these factors that affect the implementation of MOOTW by the ZDF. The identified key considerations are; national capacity, constitutionalism and multiparty democratic political system, and transparency and accountability. Details are covered in the following sub-sections:

2.6.1 National Capacity and Disaster Relief Operations

In line with the principle of separation of powers; ministries, institutions and agencies of government are supposed to carry out their duties as specified in their various statutes without the alleged interference from other government departments such as the military. In Zimbabwe various ministries, institutions and agencies of government lack the capacity to independently carry out their operations. There is always need for all these government departments to combine their strength through coordinated planning to achieve peace and development. This can be provided as military assistance to civil authorities. The need for these combined operations is more pronounced during emergency and disasters relief operations. It is a government responsibility to protect its citizens and not a preserve of an incapacitated department to provide such protection. It is therefore important for citizens to appreciate the combined efforts from government departments during emergency and disasters relief operations. For example, the Ministry of Local Government, Ministry of Health and Child Care, and the Civil Protection Agency heavily rely on military assets to carry out emergency and disasters relief operations. Therefore, the involvement of the Air Force of Zimbabwe in such operations should not raise any mixed feelings. Air Force operations are as covered above (2.5.3). It should not be viewed as militarisation of state entities. These Ministries lack the required capacity to carry out the operations. It is only recent, that the Ministry of Health and Child Care has acquired some helicopters. It is therefore important for every citizen to know that the involvement of the military in emergency and disasters relief operations is aimed to promote national security. Any government should protect its citizens by any means necessary; failures are a threat to national security.

2.6.2 Constitutionalism and Multiparty Democratic Political System

The ZDF has the constitutional mandate to protect Zimbabwe, its people, its national security and interests and its territorial integrity and to uphold the Constitution. The organization can therefore use both combat and non-combat means to fulfill its mandate. The non-combat means calls for the conduct of MOOTW. However, the strategies to conduct MOOTW in a multiparty democratic political system present some challenges. It is important to note that in China, the political system allows the PLA service personnel to be loyal to the ruling CPC. In contrast, in Zimbabwe the ZDF members should be apolitical, be non-partisan. This affects the extent to which threats to national security are perceived and defined by the citizens. A ruling party loyal military officer in an institution that is loyal to a ruling party will protect the regime and the political party in power. However, if the institution and its people are not loyal to the ruling party they will not consider any threat to a political party as a threat to national security. No doubt this has for a long time affected political stability in many African countries. By this reasoning, it follows that strategies to implement MOOTW are affected by the political system. Countries make a mistake to adopt Chinese strategies of MOOTW implementation when their political system is western. In these countries the civil-military relations together with the constitutions force the military to be apolitical. This mismatch between MOOTW implementation strategies and political systems as will be defined by the constitution is a serious national security challenge to many countries. It gives rise to coups, military intervention in politics, corruption, patronage, regime protection, power transfer resistance after elections, firing of senior military officers after winning elections among other violations to the principles of good governance. Under such circumstances military professionalism is greatly compromised and national development suffers, poverty and unequal distribution of national resources characterise social order.

China is a rising superpower. The paper suggests that, the earlier developing nations adopt the Chinese political system the better for them to achieve peace and development. Zimbabwe is already under western sanctions for alleged human rights abuses among other factors. Therefore, it might be the right time to consider the reshaping the political system to allow for free open strategies to implementation MOOTW for peace and development. This can be achieved through constitutional amendments, and provision of relevant sections in the Defence Act and in the Defence Policy. Zimbabwe is only 45 years; the legacy of the founders of the ZDF should be premised on laying a solid foundation to the young state. Never on the number of years spent by the founders in this organisation. The cornerstone for national security should be in synch with founding values and international futuristic trends.

2.6.3 Transparency and Accountability

One of the characteristics of MOOTW is high operation transparency. It is important to note that with the development of internet, and cell phone communication, the social transparency is higher. It has become increasingly difficult to try to use propaganda to try to win the hearts and minds of the citizens through publication of false information through the monopoly of radio stations. The technological environment has drastically changed that military operations and even wars can often be broadcasted from various positions. The strategies to conduct MOOTW should always be considered in the domain of the public eye. The citizens will always want to know more and for the military to be accountable to its citizens. There is need for transparency on political and economic activities by the military to both the civilians and the security members. For example, the involvement of the ZDF in the Chiadzwa Diamonds raised concerns at both national and international levels. At one point the diamonds were regarded as blood diamonds. Again the selection of officers seconded to take part in these national economic activities should be transparent, with well-known set

criterion. There is also need for some transparency on the amounts and use of revenue generated in military economic activities. Such transparency can only be achieved when such companies become public entities or when there are internal mechanisms to publish accounts if they remain private entities. The parliamentary oversight roles should always be enforced to win the hearts and minds of the citizens. Lack of transparency, therefore can be a threat to national security from both internal and external perspectives.

Strategies to Implement MOOTW

The Table below shows the various strategies that can be employed to implement MOOTW.

Although the strategies are many, 3 strategies have been selected for this study as indicated by the research questions.

Strategies to Implement MOOTW	Scholars
Community participation	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995) Zhao et al (2022)
Law enforcement	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995) Zhao et al. (2022) Bifeng (2013)
Educational awareness	Zhao et al (2022) Weinberger (2020) Joint Pub 3-07 (1995)
Prevention, infrastructure and clean-up	Bifeng (2013) Joint Pub 3-07 (1995) Gaoyue and James (2019)
Stakeholder engagement	Wang and Zhang (2022) Joint Pub 3-07 (1995) Zhao et al (2022)
Private Public Partnership	Bifeng (2013) Weinberger (2020)
Regional Alliance	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995) Gaoyue and James (2019)
Psychological Operations (PSYOP) Strategies	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995)
Civil Affairs Strategies	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995)
Coordination with NGOs and PVOs Strategies	Joint Pub 3-07 (1995)

Table 1: Strategies to Implement MOOTW

2.7 SUMMARY

The chapter traced the origins of the concept of MOOTW and explored the works of various scholars on strategies to implement MOOTW. The strategies adopted vary from country to country. The state of nature determines the suitable MOOTW strategy to promote national security. The study was framed under civil-military relations subjective and objective models as given by Huntington (1957). Civil-military relations define the nature and degree of civilian control on the military. Civil-military relations control the extent to which military can intervene in national civilian affairs. A range of strategies were identified and these include, unity integrity strategies, regional alliances strategies, public affairs/ media coverage strategies, civil affairs strategies, psychological operations (psyop) strategies, coordination with NGOs and PVOs strategies and education and training strategies among others. As in other countries where MOOTW was implemented, the suitable strategies in Zimbabwe will be determined by the state of nature, MOOTW type and prevailing conditions. The next chapter is going to focus on methodology employed in this study.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Chapter 2 was a review of some of the literature available on strategies to implement military operations other than war. The methodology chapter outlines the methods and procedures adopted in the study. The research methodology chapter covers research philosophy, designs, approaches, research methods, population and sampling method as well as data collection methods and instruments used in the study to establish strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The chapter also outlines how validity and reliability were achieved as well as the ethical considerations adopted.

3.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

There are three main philosophies that guide a research study namely the positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism (Creswell, 2009). The research adopted the pragmatism philosophy which combines both positivist and interpretivist philosophies. Positivism allowed the collection of quantitative, structured, objective data on MOOTW strategies in Zimbabwe; while interpretivism philosophy allowed the collection of qualitative data through interviews which were descriptive. The pragmatism research philosophy enabled the researcher to adjust to new issues and ideas as they emerge during the data collection process.

3.3 THE RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design adopted was exploratory since enough facts were required to be gathered from the respondents to acquire more knowledge with regards to possible strategies that can be adopted to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

3.4 THE RESEARCH APPROACH

This research adopted a mixed approach which allowed the researcher to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. The approach is more reliable as compared to a purely qualitative or quantitative approach because it answers two critical questions of the study, the ‘which’ and the ‘why’ questions. Which strategies are most applicable and why such strategies are suitable? The mixed approach was adopted in order to have a deeper understanding on strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The main purpose of the interviews in this study was to gain insights on strategies to harmoniously engage the military in non-military activities.

3.5 STUDY POPULATION

The study focused on senior Zimbabwe Defence Force Headquarters (ZDF HQ) and ZNDU officers knowledgeable on military operations other war in Zimbabwe. The research adopted purposive sampling method to select respondents at ZDF HQ. It focused on data rich respondents that is, those who have both experiences and expertise in MOOTW implementation. It therefore identified 5 senior officers at policy level as respondents at ZDF HQ. At ZNDU a total of 33 seniors were targeted and questionnaires were hand delivered and 32 questionnaires were collected from the senior officers.

3.6 SOURCES OF DATA

Both primary and secondary data sources were consulted as data sources which were then triangulated to come up with convincing results for the suitable strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

3.6.1 Primary Sources of Data

The primary data was the first-hand information from the senior Zimbabwe Defence Force Headquarters (ZDF HQ) and ZNDU officers knowledgeable on military operations other war

in Zimbabwe. The researcher interviewed respondents to get original, detailed and in-depth information on strategies to harmoniously engage the military in non-military activities.

3.6.2 Secondary Sources of Data

The secondary data was obtained from reports by the ZDF Civil-Military Department (CMR), minutes of meetings by ZDF with government officials, statistics, internet searches or libraries where journals, research reports and magazines that cover MOOT were analysed. Sources consulted were cited as references. The research triangulated the secondary data with data from the primary sources.

3.7 DATA COLLECTION METHODS AND INSTRUMENTS

The researcher used interview guide and questionnaires as data collection instruments. The research adopted the pragmatism philosophy which combines both positivist and interpretivist philosophies. Therefore interview guide was used to get the views of the participants on MOOTW implementation strategies through the interpretivist philosophy. An interview guide gave the flexibility associated with the interpretivist philosophy. On the other hand the questionnaires was used to provide the quantitative data on the the views of the participants on MOOTW implementation strategies through the positivism philosophy. Some statistical data was considered useful for the study.

3.7.1 Interview Guide

The interview guide was formulated basing on the three major research questions. Face to face interviews enabled the researcher to gain participants cooperation and this probably resulted in a high response rate. Interviews facilitated the collection of more complex information and detailed explanations on possible strategies that can adopted by the ZDF in MOOTW implementation.

3.7.2 Questionnaires

The questionnaire was formulated basing on the three major research questions. The questionnaire contains closed and open ended questions to obtain both qualitative and quantitative data. The quantitative section has four options on statements/ questions that were drawn from the research questions: Agree, Strong Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The qualitative sections have some open ended questions to gather detailed explanations of various strategies. The mixed method with such a questionnaire type was useful in collecting large quantities of data from a considerable number of people over a relatively short period of time. The questionnaires also provided a uniform and consistent format upon which all respondents were subjected, thereby eliminating the researcher's bias on determining the suitable strategies to be adopted by the ZDF in MOOTW implementation.

3.8 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Validity and reliability in this study were considered as indicated in the following sections:

3.8.1 Validity

There was need to test whether the instruments used to gather data on strategies to implement MOOTW in the ZDF were good enough to collect the required data. From a pragmatist perspective, validity refers to whether the measuring instrument measures the behaviour or quality it is intended to measure and is a measure of how well the measuring instrument performs its function (Whiston, 2012). Validity is determined by the meaningful and appropriate interpretation of the data obtained from the measuring instrument as a result of the analysis. Thus, validity tests whether the expressions in the scale make suitable measurements according to the purpose of the research. To enhance validity of the questionnaires, only semi-structured questions on strategies to implement MOOTW in The ZDF were used. A pilot test study was carried out using fellow participants, military senior

officers. The observations raised on the pilot study were corrected to make sure that all significant questions strategies to implement MOOTW were correctly factored in.

3.8.2 Reliability

Reliability is largely concerned with whether a study can be repeated (Yin, 2003). Reliability is concerned with demonstrating that the researcher has not invented or misrepresented data or been careless in data recording or analysis (Mason, 2002). Lewis and Ritchie (2003), suggest that the researcher can enhance reliability by reflecting on and outlining in a transparent way the procedures that led to the research findings; by checking through his/her interpretations; by carrying out the fieldwork consistently and by systematically analysing the evidence. Reliability of the research was ensured by making use of standard research instruments which were interview guide and research questionnaires. The researcher ensured that the questions were correctly asked and that the subjects understood them clearly. Where respondents strayed from the questions, the researcher asked follow up questions to direct them back to the scope of the research. To enhance reliability of the questionnaires, there was standardisation of the questionnaires, same question on strategies to implement MOOTW were pilot tested for clear conceptualisation and clarity and they were sent to personal emails of the respondents and in some instances hand delivered to make sure that they reached the intended respondents. To enhance reliability of interviews, diaries were used to record all the information thereby minimising researcher bias and recording of own views.

3.9 DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

The researcher made appointments with the respondents. Questionnaires were either sent online or hand delivered for all the respondents. Interview guides were also sent out in advance for the respondents to familiarise themselves with the interview questions. The

appointments with respondents were made before the conduct of the actual interviews. The secondary data was obtained from reports by the ZDF Civil-Military Department (CMR), internet searches or libraries where journals, research reports and magazines that cover MOOT were analysed. Sources consulted were cited as references. The research triangulated the secondary data with data from the primary sources.

3.10 DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURES

Data analysis and presentation was guided by research objectives and corresponding research questions. The study used both quantitative and qualitative data. Structured data was presented by use of tables and graphs and analysed statistically whilst responses from interviews were sorted, coded, paraphrased (where necessary), categorised into themes and summarised to allow for a qualitative analysis of data. The thematic approach was used to identify key themes that emerged from the collected data.

3.11 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The researcher observed the ethics of research to safeguard the interests of the respondents. The researcher assured all participants that the study was purely for academic purposes. Confidentiality of the information provided was guaranteed. In this case participants were not allowed to reveal their personal identities. Letters of introduction were sought from ZNDU (refer to Appendix II1) and respondents were requested to fill in consent forms when applicable. Participation in the study was voluntary. Those participants who felt uncomfortable with the questions during the interview were freely allowed to withdraw.

3.12 SUMMARY

The chapter presents the research methodology, outlines the research philosophy, design, approach, data collection methods and instruments, data analysis, validity and reliability, and ethical considerations. The adopted methodology enabled the researcher to effectively examine strategies in MOOTW implementation in Zimbabwe. The next chapter focus on data presentation, analysis and discussion of the study.

CHAPTER 4

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The chapter contains presentation, analysis and discussion of the results obtained through questionnaires and interviews methods that were obtained to examine strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The results were presented in tables, graphs and charts. Simple statistical methods were used to analyse quantitative data. Thematic and content analysis methods were used to analyse qualitative data.

4.2 ANALYSIS OF DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

A target population of 55 senior officers at ZNDU gave a sample size of 48 seniors officers for used in this study. Sample size determined from sample Size Determination Table.

4.2.1 Educational Profiling

Table 2: Response Rate Educational Profiling

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma	5	10
Bachelor`s degree	33	69
Master`s degree	10	21
Total	48	100

Figure 1 Pie Chart: Response Rate Educational Profiling

Educational profiling indicates that 80% of the respondents have a first degree and above and only 10% are diploma holders. A high educational profile implies that the respondents can adequately provide the most suitable strategies to address the issues surrounding implementation of MOOTW. They can logically think to provide valid deductions on effective strategies to implement MOOTW.

4.2.2 Gender of Respondents

Table 3: Gender of Respondent

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Male	39	81
Female	09	19
Total	48	100

The results indicate that 81% of the respondents are males and 19 percent are females. This gender differences has no significant impact on findings of the study especially for the quantitative results. However, to a lesser extent, mothers are care givers therefore there are likely to provide information that promotes the provision of livelihoods during interviews whilst the male counterparts stress on polices analysis.

4.2.3 Number of Years in Military Service

Table 4: Number of Years of Military Service

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
less than or equal to 15 years without JCSC	0	0
above 15 years with JCSC	48	100
Total	48	100

The results indicate that all the respondents 100% have military service beyond 15 years and they have attended a major military course for senior officers, JCSC. This implies that the respondents were well experienced and exposed to military issues, national security and they have adequate knowledge on the impact of non-traditional threats to national security. Experienced respondents with JCSC appreciate the effectiveness of MOOTW to counter non-traditional threats to national security from this assumption the respondents were expected to provide valid deductions and contribution to the study.

4.2.4 Nationality of Respondents

Table 5: Nationality of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Zimbabwean	39	81%
Non Zimbabwean	9	19%
Total	48	100

Figure 2 Pie Chart: Nationality of Respondents

The results indicate that 81% of the respondents are Zimbabweans and 19 % are non-Zimbabweans. The implication is that the non-Zimbabwean respondents will provide an outsider perspective, which balances the bias which might come from Zimbabwean respondents. The non-Zimbabwean respondents are all military officers with more than 15 years military experiences in their countries. They are therefore a very good source of information to from an etic perspective.

4.3 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.3.1 Funding by Government /Non-State Actors Strategy

Table 6. Funding of MOOTW						
	Questions/ statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1.	Can government funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	32 (67%)	07 (15%)	05 (10%)	04 (8%)	48 100%
2.	Can non-state funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	08 (17%)	04 (8%)	5 (10%)	31 (65%)	48 100%

Government/Non-State Actor Funding Strategies

On government funding strategies the results from the respondents indicate that 67% strongly agreed, 15% agreed, 10% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed See Table 1 above. A total of 83%, the majority of the respondents agreed that government funding can be an effective way to implement MOOTW. On non-state actor funding strategies the results from the respondents indicate that 65% strongly disagreed, 10% disagreed, 4% agreed and 17 % strongly agreed. A total of 75%, the majority of the respondents disagreed that non-state actor funding can be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW. Government funding is the common practice among many countries as shown by literature review in Chapter 2. However, some operations are funded jointly by government and non-state actors. In

Zimbabwe several disaster management projects were funded and carried out jointly by the military and organisations such as WHO and UNDP among other humanitarian organisations.

Interview Results: Government /Non-State Actors Funding Strategy

The interview results provided in-depth information on the advantages and disadvantages of Government /Non-State Actors Funding Strategy in implementing MOOTW in Zimbabwe. Key issues that emerged from the discussions are threats to national sovereignty due misguided loyalty and allegiance, it also emerged that funding by some non-state actors do not pose any threats to national security since they always work national governments to promote development and these include UN agencies. One of the respondents posits that:

Military is a key government institution it must always be funded by the government no matter our financial position. It is always very easy for military officers to change their allegiance and loyalty to the constitution and government. This will pose threat to national security. This has resulted in coups in other nations. Non-state actors can complement government efforts (Respondent 1).

It also emerged that some respondents agreed that MOOTW can be funded by non-state actors. A non Zimbabwean respondents revealed that:

Non-state actors mainly humanitarian organisations such UN urgencies normally fund government departments to fulfill their mandate. Funding from such non-state actors does not pose any threat to national security. Such organisations play key roles to fund disaster relief operations across the world, for example Cyclone Idai relief operations got assistance from various humanitarian operations across the countries that were affected (Respondent 2).

Therefore, the implementation of MOOTW through Government /Non-State Actors Funding Strategy is effective but it has its weaknesses which needs continuous environmental assessment.

4.3.2 Civil Ministry Support Strategy

Table 7: Supporting Civil Ministries to Implement MOOTW						
	Questions/ statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1.	Can supporting civil ministries be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	29 (60%)	12 (25%)	02 (5%)	05 (10%)	48 100%
2.	Can supporting local communities/authorities be effectiveness in implementing MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	28 (58%)	13 (27%)	04 (8%)	03 (6%)	48 100%

Civil Ministry Support Strategy

On civil ministry support strategies the results from the respondents indicate that 60% strongly agreed, 12% agreed, 2% disagreed and 5% strongly disagreed See Table 2 above. A total of 85%, the majority of the respondents agreed that civil ministry support strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW.

On local communities/authorities support strategies the results from the respondents indicate that 58% strongly agreed, 27% agreed, 8% disagreed and 6% strongly disagreed See Table 2 above. A total of 85%, the majority of the respondents agreed that local communities /authorities support strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW.

The obtained results indicate that the majority of the respondents agreed that support to civil ministry or local authorities can be an effective way to implement MOOTW is in line with

the Zimbabwe Defence Policy guidelines. It states that military can be employed to provide support to civil authorities. The practice is also common with other countries such as China among others as highlighted in Chapter 2. Military support the police to deal with strikes and demonstrations, to provide search and rescue operations, and to provide medical during diseases outbreaks for example cholera outbreaks.

Interview Results: Civil Ministry Support Strategy

The interview results provided in-depth information why the strategy to support civil ministry is an effective way to implement MOOTW. Keys issues that emerged from the discussions are violent nature of the demonstrators in the country and lack of capacity by civil departments to provide essential services. One of the respondents posits that:

Without the support of the military during violent strikes and demonstrations police will be overpowered, that's pausing a threat to national security. A police station was overrun by demonstrators in Chitungwiza in 2018 the situation was restored by the nearby military unit. During public demonstrations in the late 1990s we witnessed total destruction and rampant looting as the masses marched into the streets. Our police need military support in such operations (Respondent 4).

It was further highlighted by another responded that in case of disaster relief operations civil support was the best option:

In the absence of the Air Force of Zimbabwe support our Civil Protection Authority will be grounded to zero. Air force of Zimbabwe air assets are the only providers of air service for emergency relief operations, such as search and rescue, evacuation of patients especially during road traffic disasters. Again the military assists in bridge constructions during disasters, food distribution and in many other operations were ministries lack full capacities (Respondent 3).

The interview data indicated that civil support to ministries is crucial in maintaining and promoting national security. Failure by the government ministries to effectively provide such

essential service threatens state security. Provision of services such as disaster relief operations is a strong indicator that the government through its military protects its citizens. The implementation of MOOTW through support to civil ministries is therefore an important strategy as it provides crucial support to serve citizens from various threats to their lives, livelihoods and food insecurities. The joint operations between military and civil-ministries are always necessary to complement efforts of other departments. Lack of institutional capacities can be overcome by such joint operations. Therefore there is need to inform the citizens that joint operations enable the government to adequately protect its citizens.

4.3.3 Public Awareness Campaign Strategies

Table 8: Awareness and Educational Programmes to Implement MOOTW						
	Question/ Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
1.	Can awareness and educational programmes be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	39 81%	08 17%	01 2%	0 0	48 100%
2.	Can changes in educational curriculum in educational institutions be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?	33 69%	13 27%	02 4%	0 0	48 100%

Public Awareness Campaign Strategies

The Public Awareness Campaign Strategies includes awareness campaign on military operations other than war and educational changes to curriculum. On awareness campaigns strategies the results from the respondents indicates 81% strongly agreed, 17% agreed, 2% disagreed and none strongly disagreed See Table 2 above. A total of 98%, the majority of the respondents agreed that awareness campaigns strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW.

On educational changes to curriculum strategies the results from the respondents indicate that 69% strongly agreed, 27% agreed, 4% disagreed and none strongly disagreed See Table 3 above. A total of 96%, the majority of the respondents agreed that educational changes to curriculum strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW.

The results indicate that Public Awareness Campaign Strategies are effective ways to promote the implementation of MOOTW. Therefore there is need for vigorous campaigns to inform the citizens on the importance of MOOTW on national security. Literature has that the public has mixed feelings on the non-combat roles of the military in Zimbabwe (Rupiya, 2015). Deliberates efforts by the military to engage in public awareness can help to promotes public awareness that MOOTW are key activities that promotes national security.

Interview Results: Public Awareness Campaign Strategies

The interview results provided in-depth information why the strategy to use **Public Awareness Campaign Strategies** is an effective way to implement MOOTW. Key issues that emerged from the discussions are that there is need to educate the public on the importance of MOOTW and how it is being used in other countries to promote national security. It was also pointed out that public awareness campaigns provide the opportunity for the military to interact with the citizens to get to know their expectations from the military. It was raised that such interactions help to promote civil-military relations and image of the defence force. One of the respondents posits that:

Public awareness campaign on MOOTW activities helps to promote a good image of the military. The good humanitarian work, construction work, relief operations, aid to civil work, demining work, food production, mining activities among other operations should be systematically be made public to the citizens. They build confidence in their army knowing that they are safe and protected (Respondent 3).

It emerged from the interview that Public Awareness campaigns on MOOTW activities promote transparency and build the mutual respect among the members within the military organisation itself and between the military and the entire civilian population.

Corruption, nepotism and unfair national resource distribution are the main courses of coups and military interventions in politics. The only way to curb this is to maintain high levels of transparency and integrity in all these military involvements in socio-economic and humanitarian operations. Military officers and civilian are always keen to know how the resources are distributed. Any deviations are a recipe for disaster (Responded 2).

Public awareness programmes by their nature allows dialogue between the military and the civilian sectors. The interactions promote positive image. Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2006) sees military-nationalists alliances as promoting oligarchy government. The military therefore has to show its concern to serve the general people and promote peace and development. Human security promotion is key factor for national security.

Table 9: Summary of Strategies and Preferences

Strategies	Responses				
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Government Funding	32	07	05	04	48
	39 (81%)		9 (9%)		100
Non-state Funding	06	04	05	33	48
	10 (21%)		38 (79%)		100
Public Awareness Campaigns	39	08	01	0	48
	47 (98%)		1 (2%)		100
Civil Ministries Support	29	12	02	05	48
	41 (85%)		7 (15%)		100
Strategy Preferences			Frequency Response		
			Agreed	Disagreed	
1	Public Awareness		98%	2%	
2	Civil Ministries Support		85%	15%	
3	Government Funding		81%	19%	
4	Non-state Funding		21%	79%	

Figure 3 Graph: Summary of Strategies and Preferences

The results from Table 4 above indicate that public awareness 98% agreed, civil ministries support 85% agreed, government funding 81% and non-state funding 21% agreed. The results indicate that public awareness campaign strategies are considered the most effective way to promote MOOTW implementation. Civil-ministries support strategies also got a significant support non-state funding strategy got the least support from the respondents. It emerged from the results that public awareness programmes promotes a positive image of the military, transparency, interaction of between citizens and the military, build trust. Transparency is key consideration for such operations. There is need to inform the public about MOOTW activities in the social, political and economic domain of the national affairs. These MOOTW are always set to promote national security, therefore there is always need to let the people, the beneficiaries know the overall effects of the operations. MOOTW has a wide range of activities, for example the involvement in national economic activities has to be openly explained to the public. They would want to the rationale of the involvement of the military, the use of the revenue generated and its overall benefits to the entire nation. Otherwise, the

citizens would continue to blame the MOOTW activities assuming that they are meant to benefit the few in the military and in politics. Transparency and accountability always complement each other. Once there is transparency in these operations accountability to the public becomes easy.

Civil support also important because there is needs to complement the effort by other government departments / local communities to make life better for the citizens. All the efforts promote national security especially when we consider that there is lack of capacity for many departments to independently make their operations. Therefore joint operations become the most viable options to counter the weaknesses for many organisations. However, these joint operations are often confused as military takeover, military dominance, regime protection among other negative accusations by those who wish to attack the military and the government. The overall aim of attacking the military involvement in joint operations or in with civil ministries would be to expose the government as a failure in terms of providing for the protection of its citizens. For example, in emergency and disaster relief operations people always expect government support. In order, to counter such negativities, public awareness campaigns on the importance of such operations can help to promote the safe implementation of MOOTW.

On the hand, non-state funding got least support. Support from the traditional humanitarian organisations that support government effort was not considered a threat to national security. The support form humanitarian organisations is greatly supported it complement government efforts and it has proved very successful for emergency and disaster relief operations in Zimbabwe.

Strategies according to interview data

The study established 6 strategies. It started with 3 strategies basing on the objectives of the study. Three additional strategies emerged from the participants as the original strategies unbundles each into 2 as shown below:

1. Government funding.
2. Non-state actors funding.
3. Supporting civil ministries.
4. Supporting local communities/authorities.
5. Introduce awareness programmes and changes in educational curriculum in military academies.
6. Introduce awareness programmes and changes in educational curriculum in schools.

The discussion on the results revealed that the strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe are similar to what is practiced in other countries highlighted in the study. What is important are issues to do with national capacity, constitutionalism and multiparty democratic political system, and transparency and accountability. In Zimbabwe various ministries, institutions and agencies of government lack the capacity to independently carry out their operations. MOOTW becomes relevant. This can be provided as military assistance to civil authorities. The need for these combined operations is more pronounced during emergency and disasters relief operations. As pointed out earlier, it is a government responsibility to protect its citizens and not a preserve of an incapacitated department to provide such protection. It is therefore important for citizens to appreciate the combined efforts from government departments during emergency and disasters relief operations. This can only be achieved through public awareness campaigns. For example, the Ministry of Local Government, Ministry of Health and Child Care, and the Civil Protection Agency heavily rely

on military assets to carry out emergency and disasters relief operations. Therefore, the involvement of the Air Force of Zimbabwe in such operations should not raise any mixed feelings. It should not be viewed as militarisation of state entities.

Secondly, as highlighted earlier the ZDF has the constitutional mandate to protect Zimbabwe, its people, its national security and interests and its territorial integrity and to uphold the Constitution through use both combat and non-combat means. However, the strategies to conduct MOOTW in a multiparty democratic political system present some challenges. A detailed explanation on the differences between China and Zimbabwe and their impact was given earlier (2.6.2). From the study results, it follows that strategies to implement MOOTW are affected by political system. Countries make mistake to adopt Chinese strategies of MOOTW implementation when their political system is western. Under such circumstances military professionalism is greatly compromised and national development suffers, poverty and unequal distribution of national resources characterises social order. The paper suggests that, the earlier developing nations adopt the Chinese political system the better for them to achieve peace and development. Therefore, it might be the right time to consider the reshaping the political system to allow for free open strategies to implementation MOOTW for peace and development in Zimbabwe. This can be achieved through constitutional amendments, and provision of relevant sections in the Defence Act and in the Defence Policy.

4.4 SUMMARY

The chapter presented research results and discussion on each of the strategies. Government funding, Non-state actors funding, Supporting civil ministries, Supporting local communities/authorities and Public awareness programmes were the strategies examined. Arguments for and against the strategies were also raised. The presentation and analysis were

guided by research objectives and questions, taking the research close to the conclusions and recommendations. The major themes that emerged from the data analysis process were also presented. The next chapter covers the major findings of the study, provides a summary as well as conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter is the last chapter of the study and is presenting summary of findings conclusions and recommendations on an examination of strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

5.2 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study examined strategies to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe. The study mainly focused on 3 strategies; funding, support and awareness related strategies as guided by the research objectives. The major findings are as follows:

Funding Strategies. On government funding strategies (81% agreed), whilst non-state actor funding strategies (21% agreed). Government funding is effective, favoured and is the common practice among many countries. However, some operations are funded jointly by government and non-state actors. In Zimbabwe several disaster management projects were funded and carried out jointly by the military and organisations such as WHO and UNDP among other humanitarian organisations.

Support to Civil Ministry or Local Authorities Strategies. The obtained results indicate that the majority of the respondents agreed that support to civil ministry or local authorities can be an effective way to implement MOOTW. This is in line with the Zimbabwe Defence Policy guidelines. The practice is also common with other countries such as China. Military support the police to deal with strikes and demonstrations, to provide search and rescue operations, and to provide medical services during diseases outbreaks for example cholera outbreaks.

Civil support to ministries is crucial in maintaining and promoting national security. Failure by the government ministries to effectively provide such essential service threatens state security. Provision of services such as disaster relief operations is a strong indicator that the government through its military protects its citizens.

Awareness Campaign Strategies. The majority of the respondents (98%) agreed that awareness campaigns strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW. The respondents revealed that educational changes to curriculum strategies can be an effective way to implement MOOTW. It was raised that such interactions help to promote civil-military relations and image of the defence forces. It emerged from the interview that Public Awareness campaigns on MOOTW activities promote transparency and build the mutual respect among the members within the military organisation itself and between the military and the entire civilian population. It was also pointed out that public awareness campaigns provide the opportunity for the military to interact with the citizens to get to know their expectations from the military.

National capacity, political system, and transparency. There are factors that hinder the effective implementation of the strategies in Zimbabwe. These factors are; lack of national capacity, constitutionalism and multiparty democratic political system, and transparency and accountability. In Zimbabwe various ministries, institutions and agencies of government lack the capacity to independently carry out their operations. MOOTW becomes relevant. It is therefore important for citizens to appreciate the combined efforts from government departments during emergency and disasters relief operations. This can only be achieved through public awareness campaigns so that it cannot be viewed as militarisation of state entities. Public awareness campaigns can also help to dissolve the issues on transparency and accountability on MOOTW activities.

The ZDF has the constitutional mandate to protect Zimbabwe, its people, its national security and interests and its territorial integrity and to uphold the Constitution through use both combat and non-combat means. However, the strategies to conduct MOOTW in the current multiparty democratic political system present some challenges. From the study results, it emerged that strategies to implement MOOTW are affected by the political system.

In summary, the results indicate that public awareness campaign strategies are considered the most effective way to promote MOOTW implementation. The implementations of these strategies are affected by; national capacity, constitutionalism and multiparty democratic political system, and transparency and accountability among other common factors.

5.3 CONCLUSIONS

The study aimed to examine military operations other than war implementation strategies in Zimbabwe. The study concludes that:

Public awareness campaign strategies are considered the most effective way to promote MOOTW implementation. Deliberates efforts by the military to engage in public awareness can help to promotes public awareness that MOOTW are key activities that promotes national security. There is need to educate the public on the importance of MOOTW and how it is being used in other countries to promote national security.

Support to Civil Ministry or Local Authorities Strategies are also effective ways to implement MOOTW. The implementation of MOOTW through support to civil ministries is provides crucial support to serve citizens from various threats to their lives, livelihoods and food insecurities. The join operations between military and civil-ministries are always

necessary to complement efforts of other departments. Lack of institutional capacities can be overcome by such joint operations.

Lack of Institutional Capacity. In Zimbabwe various ministries, institutions and agencies of government lack the capacity to independently carry out their operations. MOOTW becomes relevant. However, its effectiveness is hinged on public awareness and transparency. This can be provided as military assistance to civil authorities to promote national security. It is therefore important for citizens to appreciate the combined efforts from government departments, particularly during emergency and disasters relief operations. This can only be achieved through properly coordinated public awareness campaigns.

Constitutionalism and Multiparty Democratic Political System. The ZDF has the constitutional mandate to protect Zimbabwe, its people, its national security and interests and its territorial integrity and to uphold the Constitution through the use of both combat and non-combat means. However, the strategies to conduct MOOTW in a multiparty democratic political system present some challenges. The paper suggests that, there be a review of the political system. This can be achieved through constitutional amendments, and provision of relevant sections in the Defence Act and in the Defence Policy to counter some negative effects of the current political system on MOOTW implementation.

Therefore, the study concludes that the examined strategies to implement MOOTW are generally effective. However, there are some factors that hinder the effectiveness of the strategies.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends:

Public Awareness Engagements. Public awareness on MOOTW by the ZDF in the form of short term and long term engagements with both the civilian and military personnel.

Political System Review. Political system be reviewed through constitutional amendments, and provision of relevant sections in the Defence Act and in the Defence Policy to counter some negative effects of the current political system on MOOTW implementation.

5.5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY

This research focused on examining military operations other than war implementation strategies in Zimbabwe by gathering information from military personnel. However, the study did not seek the views of the civilians. The study therefore recommends further quantitative studies that seek the views of civilians in Zimbabwe.

REFERENCES

- Alexander, J., 2006. *The Unsettled Land, State Making and Politics of Land in Zimbabwe 1893-2003*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Alexander, J., 2013. *Militarisation and State Institutions: 'Professionals' and 'Soldiers' Inside the Zimbabwe Prison Service*, *Journal of Southern African Studies*, Vol.39 (4) pp.807-828.
- Alexander, J. & McGregor, J., 2013. *Introduction: Politics, Patronage and Violence in Zimbabwe*, *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 39:4, 749-763.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03057070.2013.862100d>. Retrieved 16/11/2019.
- Alexander, J., McGregor, J. and Ranger, T., 2006. *Violence and Memory: One Hundred Years in the 'Dark Forests' of Matabeleland*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Alexander, J. & Tendi, B. M., 2008. *A Tale of Two Elections: Zimbabwe at the Polls in 2008*, *Concerned Africa Scholars, Bulletin: No.80, Winter*.
- Almann, L., 2003. *Civil-Military Relations Theories*.
http://test.icds.ee/fileadmin/failid/Civil%2520Military%Theories_Akadeemia%sept%2522200... Retrieved 10 /07/2016.
- Ayers, J.R., 1996. *Military Operations Other Than War in the New World Order: An Analysis of Joint Doctrine for the Coming Era*. Graduate Research Paper. Master of Arts . Air University, USAF. <http://www.dtic.mil/dtic/tr/fulltext/u2/a309987.pdf>.
- Babbie, E.R., 2011. *Introduction to Social Research, 5th Edition*. Belmont: Thomson.
- Bangidza, B.L., 2016. *Security Sector Reform: State Security and Human Security Relations in Zimbabwe. The Case of Zimbabwe Defence Forces (ZDF) 1980-2008*. A PhD Thesis, Faculty of Social Studies. University of Zimbabwe.
- Bechir, M. A., 1997. *The Impact of the Colonial Legacy on Civil-military Relations in Africa: Chad and the Sudan as Comparative Case Studies*. Master of Arts in International Security and Civil-Military Relations Dissertation, Naval Post-Graduate School, Monterey: CA.
https://calhoun.nps.edu/bitstream/handle/10945/31919/97Dec_Bechir.pdf;sequence=1
Retrieved 11/06/2016.
- Bifeng, X., 2013. *Military Operations Other Than War*. Lecture Notes Air Force Command Course Number 15, Air Force Command College: Beijing.
- Bland, D.L., 1999. *A Unified Theory of Civil-Military Relations*. *Armed Forces and Society*. Vol. 26 (1), pp.7-25.
- Cheung, T.M., 2001. *China's Entrepreneurial Army*. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Chitiyo, K. & Rupiya, M., 2005. *Tracking Zimbabwe's Political History: The Zimbabwe Defence Forces from 1980-2003*: In Rupiya, M. (ed): *Evolution and Revolutions: A Contemporary History of Militaries in Southern Africa*, Cape Town: ISS.
- Chitiyo, K., 2006. *Zimbabwe's Military Historiography*, Southern Africa Diaspora Review, 1, pp.117-121.
- Choto, R., 1998. *Interview: Ian Smith Speaks Out*, The Zimbabwe Standard Online. <http://www.samara.co.zw/standard/front/1.html> 1-4. Retrieved 17/05/2016.
- Chung, F., 2007. *Re-Living the Second Chimurenga: Memories from Zimbabwe's Liberation Struggle*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Cottey, A., Edmunds, T. and Forster, A., 1999. *Democratic Control of Armed Forces in Central and Eastern Europe. A Framework for Understanding Civil-Military Relations in Post-Communist Europe* (No. 1). One-Europe Programme. Nottingham: University of Nottingham.
- Creswell, J.W. & Plano Clark, V. L., 2011: *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*, California: Sage.
- Croissant, A. Kuehn, D. and Lorenz, P., 2012. *Breaking with the Past? Civil-Military Relations in the Emerging Democracies of East Asia*. Honolulu: East-West Center.
- Du Pisani, A., 2007. *Democratic Governance and Security: A Conceptual Exploration*, In Cawthra, G., Du Pisani, A. and Omari, A. (eds), *Security and Democracy in Southern Africa*. Johannesburg: Wits University Press.
- Ebo, A., 2008: *Parliamentary Oversight of the Security Sector in West Africa: Addressing Democratic Governance Deficits*: In Ebo, A. & NâDiaye, B., (eds) *Parliamentary Oversight of the Security Sector in West Africa*, Geneva. Geneva Centre for Security Sector Governance. <https://www.dcaf.ch/parliamentary-oversight-security-sector-west-africa>. Retrieved 23/5/2018
- Feaver, P.D., 1999. *Civil-Military Relations, Annual Reviews*, Washington DC: Centre for Strategic and Human Studies.
- Finer, S.E., 1988. *The Man on Horseback: The Role of Military in Politics*. London: Pall Mall Press.
- Foster, G.D., 1993: *America and the World: A Security Agenda for the Twenty-First Century*, Strategic Review: pp. 20-29.
- Gaoyue, F. & James, C., 2019. *Research Report; Introduction to China's Military Operations Other Than War*. S. Rajaratnam School of International Studies. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep20013>. Retrieved 3 /4/2020
- Hu, J. & Wei, Q., 2005. *Mao Tse-Tung's Military Thinking*. Beijing: Air Force Command College.

- Huntington, S P., 1968. *Political Order in Changing Societies*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Huntington, S.P., 1957. *The Soldier and the State: The Theory and Practice of Civil-Military Relations*, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Joint Pub 3-07, 1995. *The US Joint Doctrine for Military Operations Other Than War*. http://www.bits.de/nraneu/others/jp-doctrine/jp3_07.pdf. Retrieved 2/4/2015.
- Joshua Nkomo letter to Robert Mugabe. <http://nehandaradio.com/2013/12/24/joshua-nkomo-letter-to-robert-mugabe-from-exile-in-the-uk/>. Retrieved 25/12/2016.
- Kania, E. B., 2019. *In Military-Civil Fusion, China is Learning Lessons from the United States and Starting to Innovate* <https://thestrategybridge.org/the-bridge/2019/8/27/in-military-civil-fusion-china-is-learning-lessons-from-the-united-states-and-starting-to-innovate>. Retrieved 23/03/2020.
- Kiselycznyk, M & Saunders P.C., 2010. *Civil-Military Relations in China: Assessing the*
- Lee, R.M., 1995. *Doing Research on Sensitive Topics*, London: Sage.
- Lungu, H. & Ngoma, N., 2005. *The Zambian Military: Trials, Tribulations and Hope*, In Rupiya, M (ed), *Evolutions and Revolutions: A Contemporary History of Militaries in Southern Africa*, Pretoria: Institute for Security Studies.
- Matema, C., 2015. *Challenges and Prospects of Civil-Military Relations in Zimbabwe (2000-2014)*, Zimbabwe National Defence University, MA Dissertation, Unpublished.
- Merriam, S.B., 2009: *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and implementation*. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons.
- Mlambo, A. S., 2014. *A History of Zimbabwe*. Cambridge University Press: New York.
- Mlambo, A., 2009. *Becoming Zimbabwean*, In Raftopoulos, B. & Mlambo, A., (eds.), *Becoming Zimbabwean: A History from the Pre-colonial Period to 2008*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Moyo, E., 2020. *Commander Air Force of Zimbabwe's Vision Beyond 2025*, Presentation by the Commander Air Force of Zimbabwe Air Marshal E. Moyo, to the Zimbabwe National Defence Course Number 07/2019, ZNDU.
- Moyo, G., 2015. *Civil-Military Relations Dynamics and the Prospects for a Democratic Developmental in Zimbabwe*, In Rupiya, M., Moyo, G. and Laugesen, H. (eds), *The New African Civil Military Relations: International African Studies Perspectives*, Pretoria: APPRI.

- Mtisi, J. Nyakudya, M. and Barnes, T., 2009. *War in Rhodesia, 1965-1980*, In Raftopoulos, B. & Mlambo, A., (eds.), *Becoming Zimbabwe: A History from the Pre-Colonial Period to 2008*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Mwange, M.V. 2009. *Civil-Military Relations in Namibia, 1990-2005*. PhD Thesis. University of Witwatersrand, Johannesburg.
<http://wiredspace.wits.ac.za/bitstream/handle/10539/7253/PhD%20thesis.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>. Retrieved 23/03/2020.
- Nathan, L., 1996. *Civil-Military Relations in the New South Africa*, In Gulteridge, W. (ed): *South Africa`s Defence and Security into 21st Century*. Dartmouth: Aldershot.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S.J., 2003b. *Dynamics of the Zimbabwe Crisis in the 21st Century*. African Journal of Conflict Resolution, Vol. 3 (1) pp. 99-134.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S.J., 2004. *Putting People First: From Regime Security to Human Security: A Quest for Social Peace in Zimbabwe, 1980–2002., The Quest for Peace in Africa: Transformations, Democracy and Public Policy*, Utrecht: International for OSSREA.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S.J., 2006. *Nationalist-Military Alliance and the Fate of Democracy in Zimbabwe*, African Journal of Conflict Resolution, Vol. 6 (1) pp. 49-80.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S. J., 2010. *The Ghost of Mao-Tse Tung and the Nightmare of Military Ethnocracy in Zimbabwe*.
<http://www.kubatana.org/html/archive/opin/100830sng1.asp?sector=opin&y>. Retrieved 3/4/2015.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S. J., 2012. *Rethinking Chimurenga and Gukurahundi in Zimbabwe: A Critique of Partisan History*, African Studies Review, Vol. 55 (3) pp.1-26.
- Ndlovu-Gatsheni, S. J., 2013. *Why De-coloniality in the 21st Century*, The Thinker for Thought Leaders, Vol.48 (1) pp.10-15.
- Ngoma, N., 2004. *Civil-Military Relations: Searching for a Conceptual Framework with an African Bias*: In Chileshe, G., Chimanse, M., Ngoma, N., Lwando, P. and Mbewe, T. (eds): *Civil-Military Relations in Zambia: A Review of Zambia`s Contemporary CMR History and Challenges of Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration*. Pretoria: Institute for Security Studies.
- Ngoma, N., 2006. *Civil Military Relations: Navigating Unchanged Waters*. African Security Review, Vol.15 (4) pp. 98-111.
- Nix, D.E., 2012. *American Civil-Military Relations: Samuel P. Huntington and the Political Dimensions of Military Professionalism*, Naval War College Review, Spring 2012, Vol.65 (2) pp. 88-104.

- Nyakudya, M., 2019. *Civilian-Military Relations in Zimbabwe: A Historical Study of the Security Sector and the Quest for Human Security, 1980 To 2013*. PhD Thesis. University of South Africa.
- Ouedraogo, E., 2014. *Advancing Military Professionalism in Africa*. A Research Paper from the Africa Centre Strategic Studies. Research Paper No.6. Washington , D.C.
- Owens, M.T., 2013. *What Military Officers Need to Know about CMR?*
<http://www.fpri.org/articles/2013/07/what-military-officers-need-know-about-civil-military-relations>. Retrieved 17 /05/2016.
- PLA Military Terms, 2011. Beijing: AMS Press.
- Raftopoulos, B., 2009. *Crisis in Zimbabwe, 1998-2008*, In Raftopoulos, B. & Mlambo, A., (eds.), *Becoming Zimbabwe: A History from the Pre-colonial Period to 2008*, Harare: Weaver Press.
- Robins, S., 1996. *Heroes, Heretics and Historians of the Zimbabwe Revolution*. Zambezia, Vol. 23 (1), pp.73-92.
- Rubin, C. & Babbie, S., 2011. *Research Methods for Social Work*, 7th ed. Belmont: Brooks.
- Rupiya, M., 1994. *Demobilisation and Integration: Operation Merger and the Zimbabwe National Defence Forces, 1980 1987*. African Security Review 4.
- Rupiya, M., 2001. *The Military Factor in Zimbabwe's Political and Electoral Affairs*, African Affairs, Vol. 25 (6).
- Rupiya, M., 2004. *A Survey of Civil-Military Relations in the SADC Sub-region*, In Chileshe, G., Chimanse, M., Ngoma, N., Lwando, P. and Mbewe, T. (eds): *Civil-Military Relations in Zambia: A Review of Zambia's Contemporary CMR History and Challenges of Disarmament, Demobilisation and Reintegration*. Pretoria: Institute for Security Studies.
- Rupiya, M., 2005. *Zimbabwe: Governance through Military Operations*, African Security Review, Vol. 14, No. 3.
- Rupiya, M., 2013. *Zimbabwe's Military: Examining its Veto Power in the Transition to Democracy, 2008-2013*. Pretoria: APPRI.
- Rupiya, M., 2015. *The New African Civil Military Relations: International African Studies Perspectives*, Pretoria: APPRI.
- Sachikonye, L. M., 2011. *When a State Turns on its Citizens 60 Years of Institutionalised Violence in Zimbabwe*, Auckland: Jacana Media.

- Schiff, R., 1995. *Concordance Theory, A Response to Recent Criticism: Armed Forces and Society*. <http://www.dtic.mil/cgi-bin/GetTRDoc?AD=ADA359135>. Retrieved 17/06/2016.
- Sithole, M., 1997. *Zimbabwe's Eroding Authoritarianism*. *Journal of Democracy*. Volume 8, Number 1, Johns Hopkins University Press. <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/16800>. Retrieved 10/5/2018.
- Smith, B.C., 2007. *Good Governance and Development*. New York: Palgrave MacMillan.
- South Commission, 1990. *The Challenge to the South: The Report of the South Commission*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Tendi, B. M., 2008. *Patriotic History and Public Intellectuals Critical of Power*, *Journal of Southern African Studies*, Vol. 34(2) pp.13-26.
- The PLA MOOTW. <http://eng.mod.gov.cn/Database/MOOTW/index.htm>. Retrieved 22/05/2018.
- The US Joint Publication 3-07, (1995) *The US Joint Doctrine for Military Operations Other Than War*. http://www.bits.de/nraneu/others/jp-doctrine/jp3_07.pdf. Retrieved 2/4/2015.
- The Zimbabwe National Defence Policy., 1997. *Government of the Republic of Zimbabwe*, Harare: Government Printers.
- UN Commission on Human Security. 2003. *Human Security Now*. New York: UN.
- UN Special Envoy Report, 2005. *Special Envoy Report on Human Settlements Issues in Zimbabwe*. http://www.unhabitat.org/documents/zimbawe_report.pdf. Retrieved 13/05/2018.
- UNDP Human Development Report Zimbabwe. 2019. New York: UNDP. http://hdr.undp.org/sites/all/themes/hdr_theme/country-notes/ZWE.pdf. Retrieved 17/06/2020.
- US Congress S494 (107th) 2001. *Zimbabwe Democracy and Economic Recovery Act of 2001*. <https://www.govtrack.us/congress/bills/107/s494>. Retrieved 3/4/2015.
- Vhumba, G., 2014. *Influence of Party Culture on the Military in Zimbabwe*. Master's Degree Thesis. Department of International Students, Air Force Command College. People's Liberation Army Air Force.
- Wei, W. Dingxin, X. Zhiyu, Z. Cunhua, Y. Zhenduo, Z. and Chao, D., 2012. *The Chinese People's Liberation Army*. Beijing: China International Press.

- Welch, C. E., 1976. *Civilian Control of Military: Myth and Reality*. In C. E. Welch, (ed). *Civilian Control of the Military: Theory and Cases from Developing Countries*. Albany: State University of New York Press.
- Whitaker, B.H., 2014. *The 'New Model' Armies of Africa? : The British Military Advisory and Training Team and the Creation of the Zimbabwe National Army*. Doctor of Philosophy Dissertation, Texas A&M University.
- White Paper. 2014. *China's Military Strategy*.
http://eng.modgov.cn/publications/2016-07/13/content_4768294.htm. Retrieved 15/07/2016
- Williams, R., 1998. *Towards the Creation of an African Civil-Military Relations Tradition*. African Journal of Political Science. Volume 3(1) pp. 20-41.
- Williams, R., 2003. *Conclusion: Mapping a New African Civil-Military Relations Architecture*, In R Williams, G. Cawthra and D. Abrahams (eds), *Ourselves to Know: Civil Military Relations and Defence Transformation in Southern Africa*. Pretoria: Institute for Security Studies, pp. 265-281.
- Williamson, J. I., 2010. *Seeking Civilian Control: Rule of Law, Democracy and Civil-Military Relations in Zimbabwe*. Indiana Journal of Global Legal Studies, Volume 17(2) pp.389-411.
- Xinhua News Agency, 2012: *Xi Orders PLA to Intensify Combat Awareness*.
http://news.xinhuanet.com/english/china/2012-12/12/c_132036566.htm. Retrieved 28/4/2015.
- Yin, R.K., 2003. *Case Study Research Design and Methods*, Third Edition. London: Sage.
- Zhang, A., 2014. *Military Operations Other Than War*. PLA.
- Zimbabwe Democracy and Economic Recovery Act. 2001. Public Law 107-99-Dec. 21, 2001. S.494 (107th) Congress, 2001-2002.
<https://www.congress.gov/107/plaws/publ99/PLAW-107publ99.pdf>. Retrieved 10/03/2016.

LIST OF APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: INTERVIEW GUIDE

1. *How effective is funding as a strategic instrument in facilitating the implementation of MOOTW operations in Zimbabwe?*
2. Can government funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
3. Can non-state funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
4. *To what extent does support to civil ministries enhance the implementation of MOOTW strategies in Zimbabwe?*
5. Can supporting civil ministries be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
6. Can supporting local communities/authorities be effectiveness in implementing MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
7. *How do awareness programs and educational curriculum reforms contribute to the strategic implementation of MOOTW in Zimbabwe?*
8. Can changes in educational curriculum in military academies be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
9. Can changes in educational curriculum in schools be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?
10. What other strategies that can be employed to implement MOOT in Zimbabwe?

APPENDIX II: QUESTIONNAIRE

Introduction

You are hereby invited to take part in a research study on “**AN EXAMINATION OF STRATEGIES TO IMPLEMENT MILITARY OPERATIONS OTHER THAN WAR IN ZIMBABWE**”.

The questionnaire has been prepared by Group Captain (Dr) G Vhumba, currently pursuing National Defence Course No 11/2022 at Zimbabwe National Defence University. The information gathered herein will be used only for the intended purpose which is to assist in the production of the ‘Individual Research Paper’ in partial fulfilment of the National Defence Course. The data collected will remain confidential and will neither be published in the dissertation or any other format that identifies you. Participation in the research is voluntary. For any clarifications, the researcher is reachable at “*vumbagv@gmail.com*”.

The questionnaire is divided into three parts: A, B, and C. Part A is background information; Part B is quantitative data collection (closed questions); and Part C is qualitative data collection (open ended questions).

Part A. Background Information

Please circle the most appropriate response

1. Gender of Respondent

- a. Female
- b. Male

2. No. of years in military service

- a. less than or equal to 15 years
- b. above 15 years

3. Nationality

- a. Zimbabwean
- b. Non Zimbabwean

4 Educational profile

- a. Diploma
- b. Bachelor’s degree
- c. Master`s degree
- d. JCSC

Part B. Quantitative Data

Please tick (✓) the most relevant for each statement

Table 1. Can funding MOOTW be an effective strategy to implement these operations in Zimbabwe?					
Ser	Questions/ statement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Can government funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
2.	Can non-state funding be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
3.					

Table 2: Can supporting civil ministries in their affairs be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?					
Ser	Questions/ statement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Can supporting civil ministries be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
2.	Can supporting local communities/authorities be effectiveness in implementing MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
3					

Table 3: Can changes in educational curriculum be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?					
Ser	Questions	Agree	Strongly agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Can changes in educational curriculum in military academies be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
2.	Can changes in educational curriculum in schools be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?				
3					

Part C. Qualitative Data

Please choose by ticking (√) Yes or NO and provide detailed answers on the following questions owing to your knowledge, practical experience, and views.

1.1 Government funding can be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe? **Yes**.....

No.....

Why.....

1.2 Funding by non-state actors can be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe

Yes.....

No.....

Why.....

2.1 Supporting civil ministries can be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe.

Yes.....

No.....

Why.....

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.....

2.2 Supporting local communities/authorities be effectiveness in implementing MOOTW in Zimbabwe

Yes.....

No.....

Why.....

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3.1 Changes in educational curriculum in military academies be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe

Yes.....

No.....

Why.....

.....

.....

3.2 Changes in educational curriculum in schools be an effective strategy to implement MOOTW in Zimbabwe?

Yes.....

No.....

Why.....
.....
.....

3.3 What other strategies that can be employed to implement MOOT in Zimbabwe?

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.....
.....

END OF QUESTIONNAIRE
THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME AND INPUT

**APPENDIX 111: INTRODUCTORY LETTER FROM THE ZIMBABWE NATIONAL
DEFENCE UNIVERSITY**